

SoildiverAgro project

Adoption of new management practices to increase crop production and quality

THE WHAT AND WHY

Stakeholders' views on the agricultural practices applied in potato cultivation in the Lusitanian area: obstacles and effective proposals

Identifying the most relevant current agri-environmental problems of potato cultivation and the priority needs of end-users is necessary to assess the practical potential for integrating more sustainable farming practices into the different farming systems. In Galicia, 63 people responded to the survey: potato farmers, agricultural technical advisors and other stakeholders such as researchers or administrators with an average age of 45.7 years. The most serious problems identified were low and variable yields, lack of irrigation water, inadequate farm drainage and high pest, disease and weed pressure. The most important priorities focus on increasing soil fertility and mobilising nutrients during crop development as well as reducing the incidence of pests and diseases. The

most effective farming practices according to the survey results were shallow and minimum tillage, organic matter addition and precision farming. In addition, crop diversification and the use of pesticides were also identified as the most effective farming practices for pest and disease control and soil conservation. Despite the knowledge of the most effective agricultural practices for improving soil properties and pest and disease control, farmers' lack of knowledge about their efficacy, adaptability, management and profitability may hinder their application. Therefore, there is a need to research, advise and keep farmers informed in order to steer agriculture towards profitable and sustainable production systems.

1. Main problems identified by stakeholders in potato crop: pests, diseases, weeds and water.

KEYWORDS

Agricultural practices, Sustainable farming, Stakeholders assessment, Soil conservation, Technology adoption.

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